

SETTLEMENT OF ALLEGED SERVICES OF SERIOUS HUMAN RIGHTS VIOLATIONS NON-JUDICALLY: SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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Abstract

The Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) is a commission assigned to discover and reveal the violations committed in the past by a government, with hope to resolve conflicts left behind from the past. TRC is not an institution that replaces the function of the court because it is not a judicial body, however TRC can handle a relatively larger number of cases compared to criminal courts. **Destination Research:** Purpose study this is for to do study systematic related solution guess serious human rights violations non - judicially. This Research used method systematic literature review. Review this based on PRISMA- Protocol. Search engine used is Google Scholar. Keywords used _ _ among others, “ Severe Human Rights Violations ”, “ Severe Human Rights Cases ”, “ Non - judicially”, “Non-Judicial Paths ” , “ TRC Mechanisms”, and “ Severe Human Rights Reconciliation ”. Review this focus on published literature _ in 5 years the last one (2016-2020). Study in the form of thesis, thesis and report study excluded from study this. Based on results search found that there is nine article research that examines conjecture solution human rights violations non - judicial weight in Indonesia from 2016 to 2020. **Conclusion :** Completion of conjectures _ gross human rights violations through out-of-court /non- judicial channels (out of court settlement) with The TRC mechanism can be the best alternative for a country in efforts to resolve various cases of gross human rights violations because it is able to reveal the facts or the truth and court proceedings for incidents of gross human rights violations committed by the old government regime and can break the politics of impunity and lead the regime the new system towards a democratic system and the rule of law as a major system for upholding human rights .

Keywords: Severe Human Rights, TRC, Non Judicial, Reconciliation

BACKGROUND

Human Rights (HAM) are rights inherent in every human being since the beginning of birth which is valid for life and cannot be contested by anyone. Every citizen has an obligation to uphold the value of human rights without discriminating against status, class, descent, position and so on. Each right will be limited by the rights of others. If in exercising rights, we do not pay attention to the rights of others, then what happens is a conflict of rights or interests in the life of society, nation and state? The existence of human rights is directly proportional to the existence of the nation, according to the range of thought and development of the environment. For this reason, every human rights crime must be brought to justice because human rights crimes have been, are, and will always be an obstacle in the course of the nation's civilization. Human rights violations can also be carried out by non-governmental units, for example the killing of civilians by rebels, armed attacks by one party against another and so on (Nadziroh et al . , 2018).

The Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) is a commission assigned to discover and reveal the violations committed in the past by a government, with hope to resolve conflicts left

behind from past. Under various names, commissions these are sometimes formed by countries that emerged from time internal upheaval, civil war, or dictatorial government. The TRC is not an institution that replaces the function of the court because it is not a judicial body, not a court of law and does not have the power to send someone to prison or sentence someone for a certain crime. It's just that the Truth Commission can do some important things that generally cannot be achieved through the prosecution process in criminal courts. TRC can handle a relatively larger number of cases compared to criminal courts. In a situation where gross and widespread and systematic human rights violations occurred under the previous regime, the TRC could investigate all cases or a large number of existing cases comprehensively and not be limited to handling only a small number of cases. The TRC is in a position to provide practical assistance to victims, specifically identifying and proving which individuals or families were victims of past crimes so that they are legally entitled to any form of reparation in the future (Nasution, 2018; Suparman Marzuki, 2010).

Reconciliation as the key word for establishing a TRC is clearly related to efforts to improve social, political and psychological relations between citizens as individuals or groups and the state as a result of unfair and inhumane treatment or actions by the state. Reconciliation is needed to build the future of a democratic nation and state based on the choice of forgiveness or forgetting, and not criminal prosecution. Reconciliation requires disclosure of the truth. So what is meant here is national reconciliation where the success of the Truth Commission is partly calculated from how much capacity and success it has in creating reconciliation (Nasution, 2018).

Researcher interested for study and see description mechanism settlement of gross human rights violations through non - judicial channels that have been done in Indonesia before. Destination study this is for to do study systematic related conjecture solution gross human rights violations in a non - judicial manner.

RESEARCH METHODS

Study this use method systematic literature review. Review this based on PRISMA- Protocol. Research data this sourced from literature obtained _ via the internet (online database) in the form of article research that examines conjecture solution gross non - judicial human rights violations in Indonesia. Search engine used is Google Scholar. Keywords used _ _ among others, “ Severe Human Rights Violations ”, “ Severe Human Rights Cases ”, “ Non - judicially”, “Non-Judicial Paths ” , “ TRC Mechanisms”, and “ Severe Human Rights Reconciliation ”. Review this focus on published literature _ in 5 years the last one (2016-2020). Study in the form of thesis, thesis and report study excluded from study this.

Figure 1: Results Search with PRISMA- Protocol

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results findings covers nine article classified research _ by author and year published, title research, method study and results research. Results findings served on Table 1. Asfollowing.

Table 1: Results Finding by Author, Year Issued, Title, Method and Results Research

No	Author	Research Title	Research methods	Research result
1	Sriwidodo (2020)	State Accountability in Resolving Cases of Serious Human Rights Violations in Aceh through the Aceh Truth and Reconciliation Commission Mechanism	The research method used is juridical normative	In the judicial mechanism, there is no continuation of how the human rights court in Aceh, while Komnas HAM has no more power in non-judicial mechanisms, because the TRC Law has been revoked by the Constitutional Court and there are no regulations relating to the Truth and Reconciliation Commission yet. Efforts to fulfill the rights of victims in cases of gross human rights violations

No	Author	Research Title	Research methods	Research result
				in Aceh are based on Aceh Qanun Number 17 of 2013 concerning the Truth and Reconciliation Commission which provides compensation, restitution, and rehabilitation as well as the provision of diyat funds managed by the Aceh Reintegration Agency (Badan Reintegration Aceh). BRA), as well as an agenda for a Testimony Hearing Meeting (RDK) which was used as a special agenda to carry out the reconciliation process.
2	David (2019)	Reconciliation in Aceh: Opportunities and Challenges	Method research used _ is qualitative, using the approach to the aspect of legislation (juridical approach) and approach to other non-legal aspects (non-juridical approach).	One of the important tasks assigned by the Qanun to the Aceh TRC was to conduct investigations and gather information for truth-telling, reparations and reconciliation. This task became the basis for providing recommendations for the Aceh TRC to the government. In this context, the Aceh TRC Qanun authorizes the Aceh TRC to ensure that the government implements all of its recommendations. This authority is important to keep the truth-telling and reconciliation efforts running in the right direction. The most important thing is that the Aceh Qanun on the TRC also opens up opportunities for national reconciliation. The experience of the Aceh TRC can be a rule of model for the resolution of similar cases in the future.
3	Putra & Irwansyah (2018)	Non-Judicial Settlement of Past Serious Human Rights Violations: An Overview of the Sociology of Justice	The research method used is descriptive-qualitative.	The construction of the Ad Hoc Human Rights Court is more political and sociological than juridical. Even though there are technical and normative juridical obstacles to the proof of 6 (six) cases of past gross human rights violations. Especially after the cancellation of Law No. 27 of 2004 concerning the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (KKR) was canceled by the Constitutional Court on December 7, 2006. This has become a strong consideration for the pursuit of non-judicial settlements. The Prosecutor's step to take non-judicial settlement efforts with all elements of the government and

No	Author	Research Title	Research methods	Research result
				KomnasHAM, is an effort to break the burden of the nation's past and for the progress of the nation, sociological considerations become the first and main reference for knitting national harmony through non-judicial settlement paths with the formation of Committees and Councils for Harmony. National as mandated in Law no. 26 of 2000 concerning the Human Rights Court.
4	Nasution (2018)	Settlement of Cases of Serious Human Rights Violations through National and International Courts and Truth and Reconciliation Commissions	The research method used is juridical normative	The mechanism for resolving gross human rights violations through the TRC mechanism can be the best alternative for a country in efforts to resolve various cases of gross human rights violations because it is able to reveal the facts or the truth and court proceedings for incidents of gross human rights violations committed by the old government regime and can break the politics of impunity and usher in the new regime towards a democratic system and the rule of law as a major system for upholding human rights.
5	Radjab (2018)	Resolving Serious Human Rights Violations in the Jokowi-JK Government Era	The research method used is juridical normative	In order to guarantee the respect, protection and fulfillment of human rights as well as to resolve gross human rights violations, a new legal policy that is more operational, more protective and promotive to human rights is needed. Therefore, what should be done as a human rights law policy is, among others; First, conduct a synergistic revision of laws and regulations related to human rights issues, especially Law no. 26 of 2000 and the establishment of the new TRC Law; Second, it takes strong political will from the Jokowi-JK government in resolving gross human rights violations, which are not just slogans and political promises, but also requires the courage to take political risks for the sake of the national interest in resolving human rights cases; Third, the need for the ratification of international human rights conventions including the Rome Statute in order to be a guide in

No	Author	Research Title	Research methods	Research result
				resolving cases of gross human rights violations in the future; Fourth, strengthen the role, function and authority of Komnas HAM as a human rights institution that has the authority to investigate, investigate and prosecute like the KPK in eradicating cases of criminal acts of corruption; Fifth, it is necessary to have a national design for the settlement of gross human rights violations in addition to a court mechanism by designing a fair and victim-based national reconciliation effort by paying attention to the rights of victims such as compensation, restitution and rehabilitation for the sake of national unity by adopting several countries that have managed to get out of dark times into typical Indonesian democratic sound.
6	Aryani&Hermanto (2018)	Ideas for Ideal Arrangements for Judicial and Extrajudicial Resolution of Human Rights Violations in Indonesia	The research method used is juridical normative	Thoughts related to the ideal arrangement of extrajudicial enforcement against gross human rights violations, namely by considering the ontological and axiological aspects of Pancasila, namely the value of divinity, the value of humanity-civilization, the value of national unity, the value of deliberation and consensus, and the value of social justice in terms of extrajudicial enforcement. In addition, it is also necessary to focus on the process of revealing the truth, considering amnesty as well as providing compensation, restitution or rehabilitation to victims or families of victims who are heirs, with the courage to prioritize steps for national reconciliation instead of following the model of thinking of other countries, and in this case, must space is given for the existence of independence, impartiality, autonomy and objectivity for the extrajudicial institution of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission model.
7	Taufik (2017)	Settlement of Cases of Serious Human Rights Violations through Reconciliation Patterns	The research method used is juridical normative. The approach to the	There are two models of reconciliation found in this paper, namely: Cases of gross human rights violations prior to 2000 were resolved by reconciliation.

No	Author	Research Title	Research methods	Research result
		After the 2006 Constitutional Court Decision	problem used is the statute approach, the conceptual approach, the historical approach, and the case approach.	<p>Achieving a reconciliation requires an investigation carried out by an independent agency established by the government. The independent institution is called the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC). The second pattern found in this study and which has been successfully implemented in one area in Indonesia is reconciliation which is carried out amicably in the Palu City area. Reconciliation in Palu City started from the smallest community in society. The reconciliation process carried out was carried out and supported by the community. In addition, the role of culture and traditional ceremonies is important as a binding element for reconciliation.</p> <p>Reconciliation arrangements that already exist in several regions in Indonesia. In Law No. 21 of 2001 concerning Special Autonomy for Papua, it is mandated that the task of the Papua TRC is to clarify history and formulate and determine reconciliation steps. In Law No. 11 of 2006 concerning the Government of Aceh, it mandates the establishment of the Aceh TRC and a human rights court in Aceh. PerwaliPalu No. 25 of 2013 concerning the Regional NAP on Human Rights, contains recognition of victims of alleged human rights violations and mandates the fulfillment of human rights for victims of human rights violations.</p>
8	Nurhayati (2016)	Quo Vadis Protection of Human Rights in Resolving Past Serious Human Rights Violations Through Non-Judicial Paths	The research method used is policy review and literature review	The government's consistency in resolving past gross human rights violations aims not to leave scars for future generations, don't let it using a solution that is counterproductive to protection HAM. The use of non-judicial channels in the resolution of past gross human rights violations must still apply the general principles of human rights courts and legal certainty for victims must still be implemented as state protection for the human rights of its citizens.

No	Author	Research Title	Research methods	Research result
9	Solomon (2016)	Reconciliation based on Local Wisdom in Aceh	The research method used is qualitative	By departing from the concept of human rights, the resolution of various human rights cases cannot be separated from several objectives. First, human rights cases, it is the state's obligation to resolve them. It is not only as mandated by the constitution, but also various international agreements in the form of international human rights law that must be implemented by all nations. Second, the resolution of various problems that do not forget the purpose of national life as stated in our country's constitution, realizing a just and prosperous society, based on independence, eternal peace, and social justice. Third, the settlement by emphasizing seriousness, wisdom, and not forgetting the interests of the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. In building the TRC model, local wisdom that is referred to is the value and mechanism of Adat in Aceh known to various customary institutions that function to regulate, organize, and maintain the harmony of people's lives. The function of maintaining community harmony is implemented through preventing cases from occurring in the community.

Based on Table 1. Found that there is nine article research that examines conjecture solutionhuman rights violationsnon - judicial weight in Indonesia from 2016 to 2020. Research _ Sriwidodo (2020) states that The Aceh Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC) is a national institution/institution with a non-judicial mechanism established by the National TRC as a human rights agenda in Aceh as mandated by the 2005 Memorandum of Understanding/Mou Helsinki (RI-GAM), which is based on Article 299 paragraph (1) of Law Number 11 of 2006 concerning the Government of Aceh as a step to seek truth and reconciliation, which subsequently gave birth to Aceh Qanun Number 17 of 2013 concerning the Aceh Truth and Reconciliation Commission. The legal position of the Helsinki MoU in the legislation cannot be subordinated to any laws and regulations, because the legal political reference for the establishment of the Aceh TRC is the result of a peace agreement that must be implemented immediately. The duties, functions, and authorities of the Aceh TRC are representative of the Aceh Qanun No. 17 of 2013 as an effort to reveal the truth and reconciliation in Aceh. The government as the holder of state obligations has the

responsibility to protect, uphold and promote human rights for the community (Sriwidodo , 2020) .

The abolition of Law 27 of 2004 concerning the Truth and Reconciliation Commission created a national legal vacuum regarding the mechanisms governing the Truth and Reconciliation Commission. The government's agenda by establishing other institutions as an effort to resolve the issue of human rights violations by establishing the National Harmony Council (DKN) has received a lot of criticism from human rights activists in Indonesia. The reason is because the plan forgot important points about truth-telling and reconciliation while there was a non-judicial institution, namely the TRC. Aceh with its Aceh TRC was actually able to solve human rights problems in Aceh, but the obstacles they still faced were the negation of the work of the Aceh TRC with the National Human Rights Commission, where the Aceh TRC was based on the Aceh Government Law and the Aceh Qanun concerning the Aceh TRC which was mandated from the results of the Helsinki MoU, while Komnas HAM is based on the Law on the Human Rights Court. In the judicial mechanism, there is no continuation of how the human rights court in Aceh, while Komnas HAM has no more power in non-judicial mechanisms, because the TRC Law has been revoked by the Constitutional Court and there are no regulations relating to the Truth and Reconciliation Commission yet. Efforts to fulfil the rights of victims in cases of gross human rights violations in Aceh are based on Aceh Qanun Number 17 of 2013 concerning the Truth and Reconciliation Commission which provides compensation, restitution, and rehabilitation as well as the provision of diyat funds managed by the Aceh Reintegration Agency (Badan Reintegration Aceh). BRA), as well as an agenda for a Testimony Hearing Meeting (RDK) which is used as a special agenda to carry out the reconciliation process (Sriwidodo, 2020).

Study Daudy (2019) states that the optimism of all components of the nation must be reflected in their future support for the success of the TRC's work, even though the risks are not easy, and considering the limited jurisdiction (Aceh TRC). Although at the local level, the Acehnese are optimistic that their legacy through the truth-telling and reconciliation process will become a very valuable asset for history. And it has become a collective agreement as children of the nation that the people of Aceh should not be swept away in a pool of blood again due to the scars of heartbreaking violence. Various considerations and reasons as stated above, practically position the Aceh Regional Regulation (Qanun) Number 17 of 2013 concerning the Aceh Truth and Reconciliation Commission, is very strategic and needs full support from the government (central and regional). Because this qanun is an alternative solution to the challenges of a long history of violence that has occurred in the past. At the same time answering the legal impasse that has been trying to "fight forget" on all humanitarian issues that should receive the attention of all parties, especially the state (state responsibility) from the start. One of the important tasks assigned by the Qanun to the Aceh TRC was to conduct investigations and gather information for truth-telling, reparations and reconciliation. This task became the basis for providing recommendations for the Aceh TRC to the government. In this context, the Aceh TRC Qanun authorizes the Aceh TRC to ensure that the government implements all of its recommendations. This authority is important to keep the truth-telling and reconciliation efforts going in the right direction. The most

important thing is that the Aceh Qanun on the TRC also opens up opportunities for national reconciliation. The experience of the Aceh TRC can serve as a rule of model for the resolution of similar cases in the future. Because of the problems faced by the people of Aceh during this transition period, it stimulates all the nation's energy to think holistically and futuristically, where every problem faced must be found a wise solution instead of procrastinating to be resolved. Public demands for the resolution of human rights violations are not an easy task. The post-reform Indonesian government faces a complicated problem. This situation also applies in other parts of the world, even infecting the elite Aceh at the local level. In the end, the transitional government tends to try to solve serious human rights crimes, by trying to reconcile, it cannot be denied when these efforts are seen as a form of 'temporary justice', which is certain to be difficult to fulfil the victims' sense of justice ideally. The considerations can vary, one of the most interesting is the assumption that a legal approach alone is believed to not work (David, 2019).

Putra & Irwansyah 's research (2018) states that the settlement of past gross human rights violations which were categorized as crimes against humanity that occurred before Law No. 26 of 2000 concerning the Human Rights Court was enacted applies the retroactive principle and is within the competence of the Ad Hoc Human Rights Court to try them. By considering the sociological legal review and the sociology of justice for the "free" decision of the Ad Hoc Human Rights Court Panel of Judges at the Cassation and Judicial Review level on 2 (two) cases of past serious human rights violations, East Timor and Tanjung Priok, it can be understood that the verdict is actually a extraction of interpretations of legal norms, moral values and social interests that live in society and become the nation's view. The construction of the Ad Hoc Human Rights Court is more political and sociological than juridical. Even though there are technical and normative juridical obstacles to the proof of 6 (six) cases of past gross human rights violations. Moreover, after the annulment of Law No. 27 of 2004 concerning the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (KKR), the Constitutional Court has cancelled it on December 7, 2006. This has become a strong consideration for the pursuit of non-judicial settlements. The Prosecutor's step to take non-judicial settlement efforts with all elements of the government and Komnas HAM, is an effort to break the burden of the nation's past and for the progress of the nation, consideration Sociology becomes the first and main reference for knitting national harmony through non-judicial settlements with the formation of the Committee and National Harmony Council as mandated in Law no. 26 of 2000 concerning the Human Rights Court (Putra & Irwansyah, 2018).

Study Nasution (2018) states that the violation of human rights is a serious problem in the Indonesian government where the government has tried to resolve various cases of gross human rights violations through legal instruments, namely Law Number 39 of 1999 concerning Human Rights and Law Number 26 of 2000 concerning the Human Rights Court, although it has not been able to functioning and running optimally in resolving cases of gross human rights violations that occurred in Indonesia. The existence of the International Criminal Court (ICC) as well as several other ad-hoc International Courts ranging from the Nurenberg International Court in Germany, the Tokyo Military Court, the International Criminal Court for Rwanda, the International Criminal Court for the countries of the former

Yugoslavia, and the International Criminal Court for the countries of the former Yugoslavia. Mixed International has shown that no one can escape his responsibility for acts of human rights violations committed where everyone has an obligation to account for every form of gross human rights violation committed through a court mechanism. The mechanism for resolving gross human rights violations through the TRC mechanism can be the best alternative for a country in efforts to resolve various cases of gross human rights violations because it is able to reveal facts or truths and court proceedings for incidents of gross human rights violations committed by the old government regime and can break the politics of impunity and usher in the new regime towards a democratic system and the rule of law as a major system for upholding human rights (Nasution, 2018) .

Study Radjab (2018) states that In order to guarantee respect, protection and fulfilment of human rights as well as to resolve gross human rights violations, a new legal policy that is more operational, more protective and promotive to human rights is needed. Therefore, what should be done as a human rights law policy is, among others; First, conduct a synergistic revision of laws and regulations related to human rights issues, especially Law no. 26 of 2000 and the establishment of the new TRC Law; Second, it takes strong political will from the Jokowi-JK government in resolving gross human rights violations, which are not just slogans and political promises, but also requires the courage to take political risks for the sake of the national interest in resolving human rights cases; Third, the need for the ratification of international human rights conventions including the Rome Statute in order to be a guide in resolving cases of gross human rights violations in the future; Fourth, strengthen the role, function and authority of Komnas HAM as a human rights institution that has the authority to investigate, investigate and prosecute like the KPK in eradicating cases of criminal acts of corruption; Fifth, it is necessary to have a national design for the settlement of gross human rights violations in addition to a court mechanism by designing a fair and victim-based national reconciliation effort by paying attention to the rights of victims such as compensation, restitution and rehabilitation for the sake of national unity by adopting several countries that have managed to get out of dark times into typical Indonesian democratic sound (Radjab , 2018) .

Study Aryani&Hermanto (2018) states that the jurisdiction of the national Human Rights Court is narrower than that of the ICC when viewed from the point of view of the case being tried. The ICC is authorized to prosecute war crimes, crimes of aggression, crimes of genocide and crimes against humanity. War crimes, and crimes against peace/aggression, are an international authority, because the perpetrator is the State. Meanwhile, the extrajudicial settlement has not materialized but has been regulated in the Law on the Human Rights Court which has been cancelled by the Constitutional Court and then the emergence of the Draft Law on the Truth and Reconciliation Commission in the 2009-2014 National Legislation Program, but in the process of deliberation at the House of Representatives did not find any The bright spot regarding the limits of authority for resolving past cases is to what extent, because serious human rights violations do not have an expiration date, so that the existence of this institution is doubtful whether its effectiveness will bring about peace or vice versa to dig up old wounds for gross human rights violations in Indonesia. There are several ideas that

serve as the ideal regulatory framework for judicial enforcement against gross human rights violations, namely by considering the inclusion of the principle of limited responsibility of subordinates, expanding and strengthening the existence of the pre-trial chamber institution by combining the ideas of the Law on Human Rights Courts. And the Rome Statute and the extension of the crime element of genocide. Meanwhile, thoughts related to the ideal arrangement of extrajudicial enforcement against gross human rights violations, namely by considering the ontological and axiological aspects of Pancasila, namely the value of divinity, the value of humanity-civilization, the value of national unity, the value of deliberation and consensus, and the value of social justice in terms of extrajudicial enforcement. In addition, there is also the need to focus on the truth-telling process, consideration of amnesty as well as the provision of compensation, restitution or rehabilitation to victims or families of victims who are heirs, with the courage to prioritize steps for national reconciliation instead of following the model of thinking of other countries, and in this case, there must be room for independence, impartiality, autonomy and objectivity for the extrajudicial institution of the Truth and Reconciliation Commission model (Aryani&Hermanto, 2018).

Study Taufik (2017) states that there are two models of reconciliation patterns found in this paper, namely: cases of gross human rights violations before 2000 were resolved by reconciliation. Achieving a reconciliation requires an investigation carried out by an independent agency established by the government. The independent institution is called the Truth and Reconciliation Commission (TRC). The second pattern found in this study and which has been successfully implemented in one area in Indonesia is reconciliation which is carried out amicably in the Palu City area. Reconciliation in Palu City started from the smallest community in society. The reconciliation process carried out was carried out and supported by the community. In addition, the role of culture and traditional ceremonies is important as a binding element for reconciliation. Reconciliation arrangements that already exist in several regions in Indonesia. In Law No. 21 of 2001 concerning Special Autonomy for Papua, it is mandated that the task of the Papua TRC is to clarify history and formulate and determine reconciliation steps. In Law No. 11 of 2006 concerning the Government of Aceh, it mandates the establishment of the Aceh TRC and a human rights court in Aceh. PerwaliPalu No. 25 of 2013 concerning the Regional NAP on Human Rights, contains recognition of victims of alleged human rights violations and mandates the fulfilment of human rights for victims of human rights violations (Taufik, 2017).

Study Nurhayati (2016) stated that Serious human rights violations in the past (before 1999-reformation era) did have the potential to occur due to several factors, including very poor regulations, the role of the government and law enforcers who were quite authoritarian, and the role of the community was very lacking due to the confines of power and lack of facilities. Even now, the cases of gross human rights violations have not been resolved due to many complex factors. Many recommendations for the resolution of these cases have also been given, and it all depends on the goodwill of the government to implement these recommendations in order to uphold justice. The choice of resolving cases of past gross human rights violations by non-judicial channels raises many doubts about the realization of justice for the victims. Thus, the general principles of human rights justice and legal certainty

for victims must still be implemented as the state's protection of the human rights of its citizens (Nurhayati , 2016) .

Study Sulaiman (2016) stated that departing from the concept of human rights, the resolution of various human rights cases cannot be separated from several objectives. First, human rights cases, it is the state's obligation to resolve them. It is not only as mandated by the constitution, but also various international agreements in the form of international human rights law that must be implemented by all nations. Second, the resolution of various problems that do not forget the purpose of national life as stated in our country's constitution, realizing a just and prosperous society, based on independence, eternal peace, and social justice. Third, the settlement by emphasizing seriousness, wisdom, and not forgetting the interests of the integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. With so many victims, we should rethink from the beginning about what has happened, to solve various problems in their entirety. The delay in the completion not only causes many things to be delayed, but also the feeling of happiness for the nation's children to be united in various development agendas. Study this would like to offer one model. In building the TRC model, local wisdom that is referred to is the value and mechanism of Adat in Aceh known to various customary institutions that function to regulate, organize, and maintain the harmony of people's lives. The function of maintaining community harmony is implemented through preventing cases in the community (Sulaiman, 2016).

CONCLUSION

The mechanism for handling cases of gross human rights violations has been regulated in Law no. 26 in 2000, but in fact until now There are many cases of gross human rights violations that have not been resolved in the guarantee justice and legal certainty for citizens in Indonesia. By providing input regarding the synergy between the two related institutions in dealing with crimes of gross human rights violations as a non-military threat with legal , social and political dimensions that can interfere with state sovereignty and the safety of the nation and state, namely the entry of foreign legal jurisdictions into the Indonesian state and considered if has entered universal jurisdiction or foreign law by shifting national law, then Indonesia is considered as unable and unwilling , so that the perpetrators will be tried according to foreign law or jurisdiction and the legal authority of a country, especially the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia. Is lost or exclusion. So that settlement of gross human rights violations through out-of-court /non- judicial channels (out of court settlement) with The TRC mechanism can be the best alternative for a country in efforts to resolve various cases of gross human rights violations because it is able to reveal the facts or the truth and court proceedings for incidents of gross human rights violations committed by the old government regime and can break the politics of impunity and deliver the regime. new towards a democratic system and the rule of law as a major system for upholding human rights .

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